

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Use of no-tillage in Estonia and factors affecting its adoption: Results from a farmer survey

Economic, environmental, and political factors, along with farm characteristics, influence the choice of farming practices. While no-tillage is not so prevalent in Estonia, its use has been increasing over the last decade along with farmers' knowledge on it.

A questionnaire survey of farmers conducted in the SoilDiverAgro project studied soil management practices and factors affecting farmers choices. 276 responses were collected from the Estonian farmers in the Nemoral region. 15% of respondents were using no-tillage at the time of the survey.

The size of the farm had a significant impact as the average size of the arable land of farmers using no-tillage was 684 ha, and

thus significantly higher than the average size of 292 ha of other farmers not using no-tillage. There was no significant difference between the no-tillage users and non-users' assessments on their soil quality as in both groups half of the farmers assessed their soil quality to be fair and just over one third of farmers indicated that the quality of their soil is good or very good. The farmers growing wheat, barley, legumes, rapeseed were more likely to use no-tillage. Around a quarter of farmers using no-tillage had applied it over 15 years or more. For farmers using no-tillage, the most important considerations in their choice for the application of no-tillage were the yield, weed problems and soil quality. The most significant external factors that facilitated the application of no-tillage were availability to tested knowledge on the practice, climate conditions and input prices.

1. Collection of samples from the no-tillage field; SoilDiverAgro CS12A in Estonia. Photo: Shanskiy, M.

KEYWORDS

Soil management, farm survey, Estonia, no tillage

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